

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJANA PRASAD bearing USN 6SU21FC801 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANN SONA AUGUSTINE bearing USN 6SU21FC802 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARYA R J bearing USN 6SU21FC803 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ATHIRA P V bearing USN 6SU21FC804 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms CHELSEA B ABY bearing USN 6SU21FC805 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAHESHKUMAR RAGHAVENDRA S bearing USN 6SU21FC806 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MALAVIKA SUNIL KUMAR bearing USN 6SU21FC807 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SURYA K U bearing USN 6SU21FC808 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ARCHANA M B bearing USN 6SU21FC809 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NOUFI N bearing USN 6SU21FC810 has completed his/her internship at Rural Police Station Mangalore in the first Semester of the MSC Forensic Science and Criminology programme for the academic year 2021-22.

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